

ANCHORAGE OF ELECTROCHEMICALLY GROWN ZNO NANOWIRES ON CF AND WETTABILITY WITH EPOXY

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Interfacial strength increasing for carbon fiber-reinforced composites material can be arising out of improved wettability between CF (carbon fiber) and epoxy can. There are several ways to increase the wettability between CF and epoxy like surface chemical modification of CF and/or direct growth of CNT on CF. However, it is difficult to make CNT/CF-epoxy composite due to the flexible characteristics of CNT on CF. It is proposed suitable way to increase the mechanical strength of the carbon fiber-reinforced composite that anchored ZnO nanowires on CF. In this paper, vertically aligned ZnO nanowires on CF by electrodeposition method were used to make C-C composites. The length and width of ZnO nanowires can be controlled by varying the concentration of solution and/or electrodeposition condition like voltage and currents. ZnO nanowire decorated CF showed enhanced wettability with epoxy dramatically than that of bare CF..

Fig.1. SEM images of electrochemically grown ZnO nanowires on CF.